

The Significance of Uplifting Faculty

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Abstract - Faculty lead with vision and teach with compassion. Faculty traditionally design their courses through innovation, research, theory and practice to transform students learning experiences through a shared learning approach. Institutions of higher education hire a collective body of faculty that have a shared vision of teaching and learning, through the universities mission or core values. The recognition of faculty is momentous as it leads to faculty retention among full-time faculty and adjuncts. When Institutions uplift faculty, this creates spaces of value, support, and motivation that transcend in university classrooms that not only empower faculty, but this behavior also motivates students.

Faculty Recognition: The Significance of Uplifting Faculty

Higher education recognizes faculty through numerous awards that acknowledges faculty contributions to the teaching profession, that elevates the teaching and learning approaches while enhancing students' success. Through traditional faculty awards selection, evaluation, and the nominating of faculty are recognized, this process leads to the missing faculty that also demonstrates excellence in the profession. Higher education often communicates a community of collaboration models when recognizing faculty for excellence, yet faculty that have served in teaching positions for numerous of years are often overlooked. There are benefits in uplifting faculty, Tack & Patitu (1992) found that faculty satisfaction is vital to faculty retention and efficiency. Recognition also is in direct alignment with wellbeing as the mental health link (2025) suggested that the lack of recognition has a negative impact on mental health. This leads to faculty burn-out.

The Benefits of Faculty Recognition

Coffey (2024) found that almost half of faculty members nationally feel burned out due to their roles. To combat faculty feeling burned out and overlooked, institutions should intentionally uplift faculty professional attributions to the work, consideration should be given to creating or sustaining a faculty café. The Faculty Café can be highlighted on the institutions website, that highlights faculty contributions to the field. Recognition leads to restoration of faculty vitality. Displaying these recognitions not only inspires faculty, this action motivates the entire learning community. Most

institutions announce faculty achievements in a blitz such as a blurb or highlight on their respective website or a slide show during faculty convocation. A dedicated space to highlight faculty demonstrates institutional commitment to faculty and service.

When Faculty accomplishments are shared such as published journal articles, presentations, conference speakers, and awards, this action increases faculty investment to the institution. The Faculty Café is a faculty governed connection page that highlights faculty achievements and serves as a resource for faculty to expand their expertise in how to continuously engage students. This level of connection between faculty and recognition from the institution contributes to spaces of honor, which supports

camaraderie and collegiality. Higher education walks a fine line between academic freedom and censorship. The Faculty Café amplifies faculty voices through academic freedom, without the fear of censorship. Quinn (2024) found that in disseminating a survey facilitated by Inside Higher Ed and Hanover research responded to a survey. The survey centered around academic freedom indicated that faculty agreed that academic freedom in higher education is under threat. The responses were recorded as nearly 60% of the 1,100 respondents felt this way. Through the safe space of Faculty Café, support from institutional leadership and faculty supporting each other can establish trust between faculty and administration.

How to connect Faculty Café with the learning community

Through uplifting the Faculty Café, this virtual recognition reaches the masses of people. An example of this is the Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching, Professors Recognized as "Best" in American Higher Education Carnegie Foundation (2014). Higher education consideration of utilizing the virtual platform for faculty recognition expands beyond the institution itself. University websites receive an insurmountable amount of traffic each day, according to the Education Advisory Board (2025). The table exhibited in the Appendix below displays the definition in the first column of the total daily sessions, which is the total number of visits to the institution's website per day, and the definition of its significance in the second column. The audience that can potentially engage with the faculty café are

not only faculty, but this population can also be current and potential students, as well as new faculty. This approach impacts the broader audience through the visualization of faculty appreciation and embracing this practice as an institutional culture. The influence of positivity among new faculty can be cultivated through institutional recognition.

Maximizing the Utilization of The Faculty Café

Often new faculty that arrive on campuses are engaged in their specific discipline. The energy around faculty recognition will purposefully create faculty collaboration, innovation, and a drive for student impact in teaching and learning. Faculty Café possesses the potential to highlight faculty at all higher education institutions. Advancing scholarship and research are essential in higher education

classrooms that empower learning circles. The Faculty Café has a reach beyond recognizing faculty excellence. This display of gratitude has a lasting impact on faculty. Prestigious institutions such as Harvard embrace faculty recognition through a lens of cultivating a culture of appreciation. Although the institution offers guidelines when recognizing faculty inclusive of: *Be Genuine, Be Timely, Be Specific* (Canale et.al 2014). It is significant we uplift faculty and that institutions remain authentic in celebrating faculty contributions to the higher education space, while allowing space for reflection and acknowledgment.

The significance of uplifting faculty should be a best practice in higher education along with infusing this action into institutional core values. Faculty often contribute a vast amount of *teaching loads, research, and service* to their respective institutions, these are also the components of consideration when faculty are exploring tenure appointments. Just as tenure status is recognized, faculty that demonstrate the same components deserve the same recognition. Valuing faculty is essential in higher education; it is the intersection in institutions retaining and recruiting extraordinary faculty.

References

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Appendix

Website Performance-Metrics Glossary Traffic metrics

Sessions	Significance
Total daily sessions Total number of visits to your site per day	Year-on-year increase indicates improved website performance. This measure is a helpful adjunct to the unique-sessions statistics (see below) and because it captures repeat visits, it gives an additional indication of the intensity of activity on your site. This metric may be calculated across other time frames as well (weekly, monthly, etc.).
Unique daily sessions Total number of different individuals visiting your site per day	Significance Year-on-year increase indicates improved website performance—specifically, success in expanding the audience for your site. This metric may be calculated across other time frames as well (weekly, monthly, etc.).
% new users Percentage of total sessions generated by first-time visitors to your site	Significance High or low numbers can be good, bad, or neutral, depending on context, e.g., a high number could indicate either success in attracting new users or a problem with retaining existing users. This number should therefore be viewed alongside companion statistics that provide necessary context, including the year-on-year trend for unique sessions and the percentage of users retained.